

Researcher to Reader Conference — London — 25-26 February 2025

The premier forum for discussion of the international scholarly communications ecosystem — bringing knowledge from the Researcher to the Reader

The 2023 Researcher to Reader Conference

2023 Conference Programme

The programme for the hybrid *Researcher to Reader Conference*, on *21-22 February 2023*, is shown below. The Programme will run from 10am to 6pm UK time, on both 21 and 22 February, The programme is subject to change.

Day 1 - Tuesday 21 February 2023	
09:00	Registration, Orientation and Conversation
10:00	Introductory Session
10:40	Panel: Learning from Virtual Meetings
11:30	Workshops - First Meeting
12:30	Break with Conversation & Lightning Talks
13:30	Panel: Agents of Change for Inclusivity
14:15	Workshops - Second Meeting
15:15	Break with Conversation & Lightning Talks
16:15	Panel: Is Preservation in a Jam?
17:05	Panel: The Future of OA Funding
18:00	End of 1st day

Day 2 - Wednesday 22 February 2023	
09:00	Registration, Orientation and Conversation
10:00	Presentation: Assessing the Value of Open Access
10:45	A Changing Tide in Metrics
11:30	Workshops - Third Meeting
12:30	Break with Conversation & Lightning Talks
13:30	Debate: Open Practices Make Science Better
14:30	Panel: Data-Driven Decision-Making
15:15	Break with Conversation & Lightning Talks
16:15	Workshop Feedback
16:50	Panel: Innovating To Deliver Open Science
18:00	End of 2nd Day

A PDF version of the current Programme can be downloaded here: [PDF Programme \(https://r2rconf.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/print-programme_06-02-23.pdf\)](https://r2rconf.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/print-programme_06-02-23.pdf)

A very simple text summary can be downloaded here: [Text Summary Programme \(https://r2rconf.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/r2r-2023-programme-summary.txt\)](https://r2rconf.com/wp-content/uploads/2023/02/r2r-2023-programme-summary.txt)

Day 1 – Tuesday 21 February 2023

9.00 am – Registration, Orientation & Conversation

10.00 am – Welcome and Introductory Session

Watch video (https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=hUwolshSrVA&ab_channel=ResearchertoReader)

10.40 am – Panel: Leveraging Meeting Content

Diversifying Revenue and Extending the Mission

Watch video (<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=A8hN-pATRIk>)

Dr Heather Staines (*moderator*)

◆ Director of Community Engagement at Delta Think

Peter Berkery

◆ Executive Director at the Association of University Presses

Simon Inger

◆ Co-founder & Chief Revenue Officer at Cadmore Media

Emma Vodden

◆ Director of Publishing at Bone & Joint Publishing

As more and more academic conferences and events are being recorded, societies and associations are increasingly looking to video content to diversify revenue streams and increase member value. When the global pandemic moved meetings to the virtual, then hybrid space, researchers and event attendees grew accustomed to consuming meeting content in both synchronous and on demand environments. Member organizations are exploring different business models to monetize meeting content beyond events, enabling individual and institutional consumption, broadening awareness by geography and by discipline. From the aspirational to the practical, this conversation will build upon lessons learned and promote best practices.

11.30 am – Workshops – First Meeting

Workshop A: Strategies for Improving Sustainability

How can we better communicate SDG-related research to professionals who influence implementation and policy?

Facilitators:

- **Gerald Beasley** ♦ Former University Librarian at Cornell University
- **Nikita Lad** ♦ PhD candidate at George Mason University
- **Ratna Lindawati Lubis** ♦ Professor, Economics and Business Telkom University
- **Jo Wixon** ♦ Director, Portfolio Strategy at Wiley
- **Roger Worthington** ♦ Former Faculty member (Internal Medicine) at Yale University

If we are to achieve a future where the SDGs are fulfilled, we must ensure that policy makers and practitioners (readers) are well informed and up to date about scientific principles and research findings on sustainability. Delegates will have a chance to think about how best to share and contribute to SDG research in the context of their particular discipline. Ultimately, the intention is to facilitate change towards meeting relevant SDGs within the stated timeframe (i.e., by 2030).

Workshop B: Open Access Requirements for Books

How can we support authors with requirements for open access to books?

Facilitators:

- **Mithu Lucraft** ♦ Senior Consultant at TBI Communications
- **Valerie McCutcheon** ♦ Research Information Manager at Glasgow University
- **Ros Pyne** ♦ Global Director, Research and Open Access at Bloomsbury

Several new policies are setting out requirements for OA books, notably UK Research and Innovation's policy (January 2024) and the Office of Science and Technology Policy's recent announcement on immediate access to research outputs. This timely discussion will gather questions authors are likely to be asking, share information, and review how stakeholders, including publishers and institutions, can help to set out collaborative solutions for researchers to meet their OA requirements. This follows on from a successful 2019 R2R workshop which resulted in a cross-industry working group to create and deliver a holistic resource for authors on OA book publishing.

Workshop C: Bridging the Funder Mandate Gap

How can research data managers and publishers support funder mandates?

Facilitators:

- **Kirsty Merrett** ♦ Research Data Librarian at University of Bristol
- **Lou Peck** ♦ CEO at The International Bunch
- **Kellie Snow** ♦ Research Data Manager at Cardiff University
- **Megan Taylor** ♦ Director of Content and Research at The International Bunch

Article publication schedules, data access statements (DAS) and minting data DOIs are out of sync. How can we work together to ensure funders are able to reliably and accurately check mandates are followed by grant holders? How can we ensure funders get compliance from grant holders? How can we further open research? This session aims to educate and bring together multiple stakeholders for a collaborative, sustainable approach.

Workshop D: Research Integrity Tools

What research integrity tools could support researchers?

Facilitators:

- **Dr Jo Appleford-Cook** ♦ Training Manager, Research Integrity Group at Springer Nature
- **Christina Emery** ♦ Senior Marketing Manager at Springer Nature
- **Dr Ed Gerstner** ♦ Director of Research Environment Alliances at Springer Nature
- **Laura Graham-Clare** ♦ Director of Community Content at Springer Nature
- **Natalie Harriman** ♦ Research Integrity Manager, King's College London
- **Hazel Newton** ♦ Director of Professional Development Solutions at Springer Nature

In this session we will workshop with participants what a framework for robust institutional research integrity training could look like, and review existing resources, with the goal of developing community-led tools. We will share outcomes from our research so far, as well as feedback from a variety of stakeholders on the needs and requirements for research integrity training. This session will be of interest to researchers, research offices and research support staff from research institutions in particular.

Workshop E: Challenges in Supporting Inclusiveness

How can we approach inclusiveness in a sustainable and scalable way, without creating additional burdens on people already facing challenges?

Facilitators to be announced later.

Facilitators:

- **Dr Chhavi Chauhan** ♦ Director of Scientific Outreach at ASIP
- **Dr Tony Chen** ♦ Journal Publishing Manager at Wiley
- **Dr Suze Kundu** ♦ Director of Researcher and Community Engagement at Digital Science
- **Shaina Lange** ♦ Senior Manager, Publishing Integrity at American Chemical Society
- **Dr Anna Sharman** ♦ Founder and Director at Cofactor

Asking marginalized individuals to work to support and lead diversity, equity, inclusion, and accessibility (DEIA) risks creating an unintended ‘diversity tax’ burden. While socially-driven efforts often start as volunteer-led, this approach burdens marginalized staff and is not sustainable for the business. This workshop will explore how to approach DEIA sustainably and strategically within an organization. Participants will share their perspectives, analyse scenarios to identify opportunities for improved approaches, and come up with ways to contribute as allies, leaders, or affected individuals.

1.30 pm – Panel: Agents of Change for Inclusivity

How can we all play our part to ensure a more diverse and inclusive sector?

Watch video (<https://youtu.be/gLunsMaDh7Y>)

Dr Florence Theberge (Moderator)

♦ Publishing Development Manager (Fairer Society) at Emerald Publishing

Dr Katharina Bader

◆ Associate Professor of International HR Management at Northumbria University

Dr Yaz Osho

◆ Senior Lecturer at the University of Westminster

Ana Luíza Rossato Facco

◆ PhD Candidate in Business Management at Unisinos Business School

Recent global attention to issues around equality, diversity and inclusion has prompted organisations to re-examine their activities and look for ways to make their environments fairer and more inclusive. We know that diversity and inclusion benefits individuals, teams, organisations and society; so how can we all play our part and learn from each other? Drawing upon the results from Emerald's Global Inclusivity Report 2022 and the views of our expert panel, we will discuss the challenges academia faces, what more publishers can do and what opportunities there are to embrace an inclusive ecosystem.

2.15 pm – Workshops – Second Meeting

Workshop A: Strategies for Improving Sustainability

Workshop B: Open Access Requirements for Books

Workshop C: Bridging the Funder Mandate Gap

Workshop D: Research Integrity Tools

Workshop E: Challenges in Supporting Inclusiveness

3.15 pm – Break, Conversation and Lightning Talks

4.15 pm – Panel: Is Preservation in a Jam?

What is cooking in the long-term preservation of scholarship?

[Watch video \(https://youtu.be/ZmUq0_FEdSo\)](https://youtu.be/ZmUq0_FEdSo)

Alicia Wise (*Moderator*)

◆ Executive Director at CLOCKSS

Miguel Mardero Arellano

◆ Director at Cariniana

Stephen Marks

◆ Digital Preservation Librarian at University of Toronto

Judy Russell

◆ Dean of Libraries at University of Florida

Researchers require more from librarians, publishers, intermediaries, funders if their scholarly contributions are to be accessed and used in future. Preserving the scholarly record will never be a solved problem: it needs constant reinvention, and is going to become harder over time. The diversification of scholarly outputs means that knowledge exists in a network of contextual metadata, data, software, standards and publications – requiring multilateral management of this complex knowledge graph. We'll stir up discussion on hot topics including the confiture of collaborative print retention and storage, adding pectin into negotiations and more.

5.05 pm – Panel: The Future of OA Funding

Seeking sustainable open access publishing models

[Watch video \(https://youtu.be/Ap6TS-NqllQ\)](https://youtu.be/Ap6TS-NqllQ)

Sybille Geisenheyner (*Moderator*)

◆ Director, Open Science Strategy & Licensing at ACS Publications

Professor Ben Davis

◆ Science Director of Next Generation Chemistry at Rosalind Franklin Institute

Dr Heather Staines

◆ Director of Community Engagement at Delta Think

◆ Member of the 2023 Researcher to Reader Advisory Board

Mat Willmott

◆ Assistant Director for Open Access Agreements at California Digital Library

The open access models that are used to fund publishing activities are evolving to meet rapidly changing funder mandates and the needs of the academic community. Panellists from the research, library, publisher and vendor spaces will discuss examples of new and innovative models that seek to balance supporting a transition to more openness in scholarly communication while maintaining a sustainable ecosystem for all.

Day 2 – Wednesday 22 February 2023

9.00 am – Registration, Orientation & Conversation

10.00 am – Presentation: Assessing the Value of Open Access Agreements

Essential metrics, metadata, and infrastructure to support consortial evaluation of open access agreements

Watch video (<https://youtu.be/Wd3M94q8cTg>)

Tasha Mellins-Cohen

- ◆ Director at COUNTER
- ◆ Founder and Director at Mellins-Cohen Consulting

Laura Wong

- ◆ Product Manager at Jisc

In the transition to open access, the analysis of usage statistics becomes less about the titles to which institutions subscribed, and more about understanding usage of articles that institutions are publishing. This brings new metrics and technical challenges for publishers, institutions and consortia, and new interest from funders. COUNTER, OASB, Royal Society of Chemistry and Jisc are exploring how we work with global and article level usage data through practical application of existing standards, datasets, and infrastructure. In this presentation, we will cover the infrastructure and metadata requirements, use cases, and collaborative projects aiming to ease workflow pain points.

10.45 am – Presentation: A Changing Tide in Metrics

Responsible metrics in Higher Education institutions

Watch video (<https://youtu.be/Ce3HVT0gWNE>)

Zosia Beckles

◆ Research Information Analyst at University of Bristol

Robyn Price

◆ Bibliometrics Manager at Imperial College London

Since the publication of the Metric Tide Report in 2015, HE institutions have been grappling with the reality of interpreting its recommendations to complex questions of research culture values and reward systems. We will present the summarised findings from the annual Responsible Metrics State of the Art Survey across the years 2015-2021 and contextualise with perspective of the pressures and opportunities of responsible metrics for HE institutions. We will define how the other players in the sector such as data providers/vendors, publishers and funders can help.

11.30 am – Workshops – Third Meeting

Workshop A: Strategies for Improving Sustainability

Workshop B: Open Access Requirements for Books

Workshop C: Bridging the Funder Mandate Gap

Workshop D: Research Integrity Tools

Workshop E: Challenges in Supporting Inclusiveness

12.30 pm – Break, Conversation and Lightning Talks

1.30 pm – Debate: Open Practices Make Science Better

Watch video (<https://youtu.be/jgfEfqCjo5M>)

Rick Anderson (*Moderator*)

- ◆ University Librarian at Brigham Young University
- ◆ Member of the 2023 Researcher to Reader Advisory Board

Steven Heffner

- ◆ Managing Director, Publications at the IEEE

Catriona MacCallum

- ◆ Director of Open Science at Hindawi Publishing

Dr Malvika Sharan

- ◆ Senior Researcher, Open Research at The Alan Turing Institute

Dr Karin Wulf

- ◆ Director and Librarian at the John Carter Brown Library
- ◆ Professor of History at Brown University

2.30 pm – Panel: Data-Driven Decision-Making

Asking the transformative question: What can we achieve with quality data?

Watch video (<https://youtu.be/CmtKqxf98ao>)

Christopher Kenneally (*Moderator*)

◆ Senior Marketing Director at Copyright Clearance Center

Dr José F Salm Junior

◆ Professor at Santa Catarina State University – UDESC

Catia Laranjeira

◆ Manager PTCRIS, Scientific Knowledge Department Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (FCT, Portugal)

Veronika Spinka

◆ Senior Vice President, Science Thieme Group

Michael Healy

◆ Executive Director, Rightsholder & International Relations at Copyright Clearance Center

Like evidence-based medicine, data-driven decision-making in publishing seems a no-brainer. But just as many doctors have long trusted their intuitions, so have scholarly publishers. Doing so in 2023, however, may get your license revoked in both professions. The proposed panel discussion will drive a stakeholder dialogue addressing metadata management and what industry participants see as the solution to managing metadata. The audience will gain an appreciation for how proper application of quality data can open a 360-degree-view of the research ecosystem to address important concerns of sustainability, compliance, and access.

3.15 pm – Break, Conversation and Lightning Talks

4.15 pm – Workshop Feedback

Workshop A: Strategies for Improving Sustainability

Workshop B: Open Access Requirements for Books

Workshop C: Bridging the Funder Mandate Gap

Workshop D: Research Integrity Tools

Workshop E: Challenges in Supporting Inclusiveness

Each workshop provides a brief report of their conclusions.

[Watch video \(https://youtu.be/f7r8e7xJfcs\)](https://youtu.be/f7r8e7xJfcs)

4.50 pm – Panel: Innovating To Deliver Open Science

How can we accelerate change and ensure inclusivity?

[Watch video \(https://youtu.be/dTy_n4uUdr0\)](https://youtu.be/dTy_n4uUdr0)

Jayne Marks (Moderator)

◆ Senior Associate at Maverick Publishing Specialists

Dr Alex Freeman

◆ Director at Octopus CIC

Dr Richard Gallagher

◆ President & Editor-in-Chief at Annual Reviews

Robert Kiley

◆ Head of Strategy at CoalitionS

Wilhelm Widmark

◆ Library Director at Stockholm University

◆ Member of the 2023 Researcher to Reader Advisory Board

The move to open science has started to deliver new and innovative models. This panel will explore what this means for the key stakeholders and what they expect to see in the future. With transformative agreements ending at the end of 2024, what comes next? What will happen to hybrid journals? Is the APC model here to stay and if so how can we make it fair and equitable? Or will new models emerge?

5.40 pm – Summary and Closing

[Watch video \(https://youtu.be/yka3uWgdh8w\)](https://youtu.be/yka3uWgdh8w)

Dr Anna Sharman

◆ Founder and Director at Cofactor

Mark Carden

◆ Manging Consultant at Mosaic Search & Selection

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